

Could machine learning help us to solve the climate crisis?

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ABSTRACT:

The Climate Crisis is a real problem in different aspects with a significant impact on our life. Machine learning is a powerful tool to solve problems or identify solutions and answers for many issues. Now is the question of how we can Machine learning use that we have a beneficial impact to solve the climate crisis.

KEYWORDS:

Climate change, machine learning, greenhouse gases, climate crises, reduce greenhouse gases

1 INTRODUCTION:

We could observe heavy storms, flooding, wildfires, and other ecological calamities in the last years. In addition, the intergovernmental report on climate change

from 2018 predicted catastrophic consequences if the global greenhouse gas rises [1].

Therefore, reducing greenhouse gases in the following years is necessary to prevent this forecast. Many areas produce greenhouse gases like electrical systems, buildings, industry, and transportation (S1A2).

Machine learning evolved into a powerful tool for general problems in technology and society in the last few years (S2A1). It is essential to identify how machine learning can be applied to reduce greenhouse gases.

This paper will comment usage of machine learning in electrical systems, buildings, industry, and transportation.

2 SECTORS TO REDUCE GREENHOUSE GASES

2.1 Electricity Systems

A quarter of the annual greenhouse gas emissions are responsible for electricity systems [2]. There are three types of electricity. We distinguish between variable low-carbon power, controllable low-carbon power, and fossil fuel power.

AI in variable sources could optimize forecasting supply and demand, improving scheduling and flexible demand, and acceleration materials science.

Here are a few examples:

Forecasting supply and demand: Machine learning models can use historical data, physical model outputs, video, and image data to create short and medium-term forecasts of solar, wind, and hydropower [3].

Improving scheduling and flexible demand: Machine Learning helps the existing scheduling and dispatch processes by speeding up power system problems [4].

Acceleration materials science: Some works used ML, AI, and physics to figure out a material's crystal structure for solar fuels [5]

2.2 Transportation

The transportation sector is also responsible for about a quarter of energy-related CO₂ emissions [1]. To reduce the greenhouse gasses in this sector, they are following agenda:

- reducing transport activity

- improving vehicle efficiency
- alternative fuels and electrification
- Modal shift

Here are a few examples:

Reducing transport activity: ML could estimate the origin-destination demand from traffic counts [6].

Improving vehicle efficiency: Machine learning is essential in autonomous vehicles, including in such basic tasks as following the road and detecting obstacles [7].

Alternative fuels and electrification: Similar to Electricity Systems

Modal shift: Coordination between the modes of transport, which leads to faster and more reliable transit times, could increase the number of people or goods transported by low-carbon modes of transport such as rail. ML algorithms could be applied to make public transport faster and more user-friendly. For example, abundant literature deals with ML methods for predicting bus arrival times and their uncertainty [8].

2.3 Buildings

Buildings are easy to optimize to reduce their greenhouse gases emissions. Easy fixes and modern strategies could reduce greenhouse gasses up to 90 %. [9].

Here are a few examples:

Modeling building energy: Traditionally, energy forecasts use the physical structure from buildings, and these mostly are thermodynamics computations. Machine learning could accelerate these computations

to reduce the need for expensive simulations [10].

Smart buildings: Machine Learning can reduce energy consumption by controlling devices and systems and responding to signals from the electricity grid to provide flexibility to the grid operator and lower costs to the consumer.

2.4 Industry

The industry sector has three areas where they could reduce greenhouse gases:

- Optimizing supply chain
- Improving materials
- Production and energy

Here are a few examples:

Optimizing supply chain: Machine learning could help by reducing overproduction or overstocking goods by improving demand forecasting [11].

Improving materials: Cement and steel production are responsible for about 10% of global greenhouse gases. [12] Combined with generative design, machine learning could help reduce cement and steel for structural products.

Production and energy: Machine learning can improve the efficiency of heating, ventilation, and air conditions systems, and other industrial control mechanisms [13].

3 DISCUSSION

For any changes in the climate change crisis, we have to reduce greenhouse gases. The good thing is that there are many

opportunities to reduce greenhouse gases in every section of our lives. Moreover, we have technology like machine learning that could help us do this. One of the critical things is the quality and availability of data. Unfortunately, the availability is primarily in the industry sector, a problem because the companies would not like to share their data with other companies and could not unlock the full potential. Only 30 - 40 % of data are used in the industry sector [14]. A big topic is forecasting energy demand and controlling from energy consumers like machines and or electrical systems. Another big topic is the change of energy sources, primarily from fossil to low-carbon power. Also, efficient transportation of goods or passengers is a promising area to reduce greenhouse gases.

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